

Machine Learning for Enhanced Advertisement Effectiveness: A Computational Model to Analyze Persuasion in Visual Advertisements

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Abstract

The competitive landscape of advertising necessitates a nuanced understanding of persuasion strategies to craft impactful advertisements. In this pursuit, I present a novel framework employing deep learning models to analyze picture advertisements and both predict and locate the embedded persuasion strategies. Our approach leverages the U-Net model and the ConvNextXLarge Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to extract and analyze visual features indicative of various persuasion strategies. Through rigorous evaluation, I demonstrate that our models exhibit a promising capability to identify and categorize persuasion strategies effectively. The output of this research not only provides a computational method to gauge the persuasion tactics deployed but also paves the way for an assistive tool for companies aiming to enhance their advertisement effectiveness. By integrating our persuasion prediction model, companies can now analyze the potential effectiveness of their advertisements prior to campaign launches. This, in turn, facilitates data-driven decision-making in advertisement design, potentially leading to improved engagement rates and better Return on Advertising Spend (ROAS). Our work presents a significant stride towards marrying machine learning with advertising domain knowledge, opening avenues for further research and real-world applications in the rapidly expanding field of computational advertising.

Introduction

Research Importance

The intricacies of effective advertising in today's digital landscape extend beyond captivating visuals to encompass well-strategized persuasion tactics that resonate with the target audience. The ability to decode and employ effective persuasion strategies in advertisements can significantly bolster a brand's appeal and consumer engagement. This research, leveraging the U-Net and ConvNextXLarge Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models, aims to provide a computational tool to predict persuasion strategies in picture advertisements, thus offering businesses a mechanism to pre-assess the potential effectiveness of their advertisement

campaigns. This predictive capability could lead to optimized engagement and improved Return on Advertising Spend (ROAS), providing a competitive edge in the market.

Hypothesis

Our hypotheses center on the idea that visual elements in advertisements carry discernible cues related to their persuasion strategy. I posit that with the right model architecture and training, it's feasible to extract these cues to predict the employed persuasion strategy accurately. I specifically hypothesize our strategy will exhibit substantial capability in recognizing and categorizing different persuasion strategies within picture advertisements. If validated, the high accuracy in persuasion prediction can offer a valuable asset for businesses, enabling a data-driven approach to advertisement creation and refinement, further contributing to the evolving field of computational advertising.

Objective

The principal objective of this study is twofold. The first pillar seeks to identify the diverse persuasion strategies that appear in image advertisements. By doing so, I endeavor to understand the ways in which visual cues influence viewer perceptions and actions. The second pillar delves deeper, employing image segmentation techniques to demarcate specific regions within each advertisement image. This allows us to attribute individual components of the visual to distinct persuasion strategies, painting a more detailed picture of advertisement composition.

Related Work

In the endeavor to decipher persuasion strategies in advertisements, recent studies have embraced innovative approaches. Singla et al. (2022) employed a blend of Object Detection, Symbol Recognition, and Text Recognition to predict persuasion tactics in image adverts, pioneering the use of computer vision for such analysis. Their methodology involved extracting multiple features from images and funneling them into a multi-modal prediction model to ascertain the persuasion strategies employed. Another seminal work shifted the focus to video advertisements, advocating for the conversion of videos into textual narratives to facilitate enhanced prediction. By extracting key frames and transcribing speech, they generated textual narratives that were further analyzed to predict the persuasion strategies utilized. These explorations underline the growing recognition of the interplay between computer vision and language processing in unveiling the persuasive underpinnings of advertisements, which my research seeks to extend by employing the U-Net model and the ConvNextXLarge CNN model

for analyzing picture advertisements. The potential applications of these predictive models are substantial, offering a pathway for companies to refine their advertising strategies by gauging the persuasive effectiveness of their adverts through these models.

Data

Our primary dataset is sourced from Singla et al. (2022), where image advertisements were annotated for various persuasion strategies. Recognizing the potential of this dataset but also its limitations in serving our specific segmentation goals, I embarked on creating a supplementary dataset. In order to implement image segmentation, a select subset of images from the original compilation was annotated with image masks. To bolster the variability and comprehensiveness of this supplementary dataset, sophisticated data augmentation techniques were applied, including mirroring the images and the masks.

Numerous advertisements incorporated textual elements; however, our focus was strictly on visual analysis. Consequently, I selected a subset of the dataset emphasizing the predominant visual persuasion strategies. Our endeavor was to categorize six distinct persuasion tactics through imagery. These included emotional cues like "Amazed", "Cheerful", and "Eager", as well as visual themes like "Active", "Fashionable", and "Feminine".

In our study, each persuasion strategy encompassed a collection of roughly 100 images. However, only 40 images in each category were labeled with specific image segmentation labeling, which is what I used to train our model to locate the persuasion strategies in the images.

Here are some example of images:

Methodology

1. Data Preprocessing:

Given the meticulous efforts of Singla et al., our primary dataset was in a ready-to-use state, removing the need for preprocessing. However, our supplementary dataset, which I created to fulfill segmentation goals, underwent data augmentation. This preprocessing step was vital to introduce diversity, and enhance the model's generalizability. Furthermore, data augmentation significantly contributes to avoiding overfitting. By artificially expanding the dataset through various transformations such as rotation and flipping, I ensured a broader spectrum of data for the models to learn from. This, in turn, promotes a more robust learning process, enabling our models to better generalize across unseen data and thereby mitigating the risk of overfitting.

2. Feature Engineering:

In the realm of machine learning, especially when dealing with raw images, the model's ability to discern and extract pivotal features is paramount. Our reliance on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) was predicated on their innate prowess in automatically sieving through image data to derive features that are most salient to the task at hand.

3. Models:

3.1. Classification Model:

This model's primary task was to simply classify the top persuasion strategy embedded within each image. To accomplish this, I harnessed the power of transfer learning.

Transfer learning allows for the application of knowledge acquired from one problem to a related one, reducing the need for extensive data and computational resources. It involves utilizing pre-trained models and fine-tuning them on a specific task. This technique expedited our model development process for classifying persuasion strategies in picture advertisements. In our study, I employed two established transfer learning models: ResNet50 and ConvNextXLarge, leveraging their pre-trained architectures to accelerate and enhance the performance of our classification models.

For the basic classification task, I modified two popular neural network architectures, ResNet50 and ConvNextXLarge. The high-level features extracted by these networks flow into a dense layer with 128 nodes, serving as an intermediary transformation. This dense layer essentially acts as a bridge, ensuring that the features from the base models are appropriately shaped and processed before they are fed into the final classification layer. The model then funnels the

information from the 128-node layer into a final output layer with 6 nodes. Each of these nodes output a probability score for each of the 6 classes, and the class with the highest score is the model's prediction

To ensure that the model generalizes well and doesn't overfit to the training data, I experimented with L1 and L2 regularization techniques in the dense layer for both ResNet50 and ConvNextXLarge.

ResNet50 Validation Accuracy with different Regularization Values

		L2 Regularization						
		0	0.0005	0.001	0.005	0.01	0.05	0.1
L1 Regularization	0	0.545	0.612	0.554	0.606	0.581	0.567	0.572
	0.0005	0.591	0.525	0.625	0.537	0.544	0.594	0.599
	0.001	0.611	0.567	0.612	0.631	0.591	0.597	0.603
	0.005	0.578	0.563	0.573	0.524	0.551	0.532	0.582
	0.01	0.548	0.555	0.547	0.555	0.549	0.541	0.538
	0.05	0.432	0.414	0.438	0.450	0.451	0.475	0.443
	0.1	0.404	0.411	0.469	0.353	0.404	0.391	0.392

ConvNextXLarge Validation Accuracy with different Regularization Values

		L2 Regularization						
		0	0.0005	0.001	0.005	0.01	0.05	0.1
L1 Regularization	0	0.606	0.702	0.655	0.684	0.648	0.671	0.643
	0.0005	0.644	0.601	0.698	0.599	0.604	0.702	0.7
	0.001	0.68	0.62	0.708	0.693	0.64	0.667	0.686
	0.005	0.65	0.628	0.629	0.583	0.627	0.557	0.662
	0.01	0.613	0.586	0.633	0.639	0.586	0.604	0.621
	0.05	0.493	0.505	0.49	0.48	0.544	0.547	0.539
	0.1	0.444	0.471	0.528	0.434	0.487	0.458	0.449

3.2. Multimodal Classification with OCR:

For a more nuanced approach to classifying persuasion strategies in picture advertisements, I developed a multi-modal classification model that incorporates Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technology. This advancement allowed us to extract textual data from images, adding an additional layer of information for our model to analyze alongside visual features. By combining these two data sources, our model could achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the persuasion strategies employed in the advertisements.

I utilized the pre-trained model Tesseract for the OCR component, which involves text detection and extraction. The extracted text was then processed using NLP techniques, including tokenization and embedding, to transform it into a format suitable for neural network analysis. This textual data was combined with the visual features extracted by modified versions of ConvNextXLarge, which was the model I used for basic classification.

3.2.1. Multimodal Network Architecture

To integrate the visual and textual features effectively, I employed a two-branch multimodal neural network architecture. One branch processed the visual features extracted by the ConvNextXLarge model, while the other branch handled the embedded textual features from the OCR component. The outputs from these two branches were then concatenated and fed into a dense layer of 256 nodes, serving as an integration point for the multimodal data. This layer was followed by another dense layer, this time with 128 nodes, to further process and combine the features before reaching the final classification layer.

The final layer of the model consisted of 6 nodes, similar to our basic classification model, each representing a different persuasion strategy class. The model predicted the persuasion strategy by selecting the class corresponding to the highest probability score among these nodes.

3.2.2. Multimodal Network Hyperparameter Tuning

To mitigate overfitting and improve generalization in this more complex model, I explored various regularization techniques and hyperparameter settings. Additionally, dropout layers were introduced between the dense layers to reduce the risk of overfitting by randomly omitting a subset of features during training.

3.2.2.1. Hyper Parameter Tuning Results

Hyperparameter Tuning with Dropout Rates:

Dropout=0.2: Validation Accuracy = 75.9%

Dropout=0.3: Validation Accuracy = 75.9%

Dropout=0.4: Validation Accuracy = 79.6%

Dropout=0.5: Validation Accuracy = 77.7%

Adjusting the Number of Nodes in the Final 2 Dense Layers:

Layer 1: 512 Nodes, Layer 2: 256 Nodes: Validation Accuracy = 79.6%

Layer 1: 256 Nodes, Layer 2: 128 Nodes: Validation Accuracy = 79.6%

Layer 1: 128 Nodes, Layer 2: 64 Nodes: Validation Accuracy = 74.1%

3.3. U-NET for Segmentation:

The U-NET model was chosen due to its superior ability in intricately delineating complex patterns present in images. Given our ambitious endeavor to map specific components of advertisements to distinct persuasion strategies, employing U-NET became a logical choice. Its robust architecture facilitates the inclusion of new images that were not manually segmented earlier, thereby broadening our analytical scope. This feature is particularly advantageous as it significantly enhances our project's adaptability, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of various advertising elements and their corresponding persuasive tactics.

3.3.1. U-NET Architecture

The U-Net model architecture comprises an encoding (contracting) and decoding (expansive) path. In the input layer, images of shape (IMG_HEIGHT, IMG_WIDTH, IMG_CHANNELS) are accepted and scaled to a range of [0, 1]. The contracting path consists of four blocks, each containing two convolutional layers with a number of filters incrementally increasing from 16 to 256, accompanied by dropout layers with rates ranging from 30% to 50%, and a max-pooling layer following each block except the last. Conversely, the expansive path also consists of four blocks, each having an up-sampling layer which reduces the number of filters from 128 to 16, two convolutional layers, dropout layers with rates ranging from 30% to 40%, and skip connections from the contracting blocks to retain high-resolution features. The architecture culminates in an output layer with a 1x1 convolution alongside a sigmoid activation function for binary image segmentation. The model leverages the Adam optimizer and employs a binary cross-entropy loss function for training.

Our primary metric for model evaluation is accuracy. For the U-NET model, accuracy was quantified by contrasting our manually annotated image masks against the masks inferred by the model.

3.3.2. U-NET Hyperparameter Tuning

To optimize the U-Net model's performance for our image segmentation task, I undertook a systematic hyperparameter tuning approach. Our process aimed to assess the effects of different training parameters, including epoch numbers, batch sizes, dropout rates across different layers, and input image resolutions.

Experimentation Process

I began our tuning process by varying the number of training epochs, which was initially set at 25. To understand the effect of training duration on model performance, I doubled this number to 50. Subsequently, I assessed the influence of batch size on our results, experimenting with sizes of 12, 24, and the original 16. Furthermore, understanding that dropout rates can be pivotal in preventing overfitting, especially in deep learning models, like U-Net, I individually adjusted dropout rates in each of the 9 layers. Lastly, I also experimented with the input image resolution, reducing it from 256x256 pixels to 128x128 pixels, to determine its effect on model accuracy and computational efficiency.

Hyperparameter Tuning Results

Doubling the epochs to 50 resulted in an improved training accuracy of 85.71% and validation accuracy of 77.14%.

Changing the batch size yielded a higher training accuracy of 88.48%. However, it caused overfitting, and a decrease in validation accuracy.

Increasing dropout rates in different layers helped improve results for validation accuracy, but reduced training accuracy, which was expected. Increasing the dropout by .1 in all the layers improved validation accuracy to 79.08%.

Reducing the image resolution from 256x256 to 128x128 enhanced the validation accuracy to 80.38%, which suggests that for our specific dataset and task, a reduced image resolution might lead to better model generalization.

Final Model Configuration

Based on our experiments, I chose the configuration that achieved a balance between training and validation accuracy while avoiding overfitting. Our selected model utilized an input resolution of 128x128 pixels, a batch size of 16, and dropout rates optimized as per our findings.

3.4. Integrating Object Detection (Mask R-CNN) with OCR Classification

To enhance the precision of classifying persuasion tactics in pictorial advertisements, I opted to innovate our approach by integrating object detection data into our multi-modal model, moving away from the previously utilized transfer learning CNN. This advancement involved the adoption of Mask R-CNN for the identification of objects within images, and then leveraging this detailed information using a standard artificial neural network. This shift from a traditional convolutional neural network, which processes images in their entirety, to a more targeted analysis, potentially allows for a more refined input. I then integrated this neural network with our previous OCR + NLP network to make another multi-modal configuration. I made this change because recognizing objects in the image first might be able to enhance the neural network's ability to categorize the image more accurately than merely using convolution-based data.

Mask R-CNN, an extension of the Faster R-CNN framework, excels in instance segmentation by not only identifying object boundaries within images but also segmenting each object instance. To perform transfer learning again, I used a pre-trained Mask R-CNN model, and then re-trained it on our own data, so that it could identify and segment various objects in advertisements. Just like before, I incorporated OCR technology to capture textual content within the advertisements. The OCR component, powered by Tesseract, extracts text, and then processes it with the same NLP techniques used in the last multi-modal model (tokenization and word embedding of the textual data).

3.4.4. Multimodal Network Architecture

The multimodal network architecture involves a fusion of features extracted by Mask R-CNN and those derived from OCR text. The concatenated features are then processed through a series of dense layers (2 dense layers, and then 1 output layer of 6 nodes).

3.4.4. Multimodal Network Hyperparameter Tuning

I tuned hyperparameters such as dropout rates and the number of nodes in the final dense layers to optimize model performance.

Hyperparameter Tuning with Dropout Rates:

Dropout=0.2: Validation Accuracy = 77.7%

Dropout=0.3: Validation Accuracy = 83.3%

Dropout=0.4: Validation Accuracy = 81.4%

Dropout=0.5: Validation Accuracy = 79.6%

Adjusting the Number of Nodes in the Final 2 Dense Layers:

Layer 1: 512 Nodes, Layer 2: 256 Nodes: Validation Accuracy = 81.4%

Layer 1: 256 Nodes, Layer 2: 128 Nodes: Validation Accuracy = 83.3%

Layer 1: 128 Nodes, Layer 2: 64 Nodes: Validation Accuracy = 83.3%

Results and Analysis

In our endeavor to accurately predict the utilization of six distinct persuasion strategies—Amazed, Eager, Cheerful, Fashionable, Feminine, and Active—in advertisements, I employed a variety of transfer learning models. These models, leveraging pre-trained networks, were fine-tuned to our specific task, aiming to optimize the accuracy of strategy identification. Moreover, a U-Net model, known for its efficacy in semantic segmentation, was harnessed to discern the regions within the advertisements that prominently showcased the persuasive strategies.

I then incorporated OCR into our classification, transforming it into a multi-modal model, which significantly enhanced its ability to accurately identify persuasion strategies, by leveraging both visual cues and textual content within advertisements. This approach proved to be highly effective, as it caused a huge jump in validation accuracy, from 70.3% to 79.6%. This underscores the value of text-based analysis along with visual data in understanding and classifying complex data such as visual advertisements.

I then replaced the standard CNN part of the multi-modal model with a Mask R-CNN and a classifier, so that I could identify the objects in the image before classifying on the visual data, which enabled a more comprehensive understanding of the persuasion strategies. Through meticulous hyperparameter tuning and model optimization, I developed a robust framework capable of dissecting the multifaceted elements of persuasive messaging in advertisements. This also proved to improve the validation accuracy compared to the previous, making it go from 79.6% to a final 83.3%.

Throughout our multifaceted approach, I not only sought to determine the persuasion strategy employed but also aimed to understand the visual emphasis of such strategies in the ad's composition. This rigorous analysis was essential for drawing meaningful insights into the persuasive elements that drive consumer engagement.

Basic Classification Results

ResNet50 Transfer Learning Confusion Matrix (Accuracy = 0.630)

ConvNextXLarge Transfer Learning Confusion Matrix (Accuracy = 0.703)

U-NET Image Segmentation Results

The final accuracy of the U-Net, after the hyperparameter tuning, was 79.08%, which is very impressive.

Here is an randomly selected example of a true mask compared with the mask predicted by the U-NET model:

True Mask

60 80 100 120

Predicted Mask

60 80 100 120

Multimodal Classification Results 1

1st Multimodal Model - CNN + OCR/NLP (Accuracy = 0.796)

Multimodal Classification Results 2

2nd Multimodal Model - Mask R-CNN + OCR/NLP (Accuracy = 0.833)

Limitations

While this study offers significant insights into the identification and segmentation of persuasion strategies in image advertisements, there are notable limitations. First, the models utilized might exhibit biases rooted in the training data, potentially leading to oversights or misinterpretations of certain advertisement elements. The accuracy scores achieved, although commendable, indicate that there's still room for improvement. Moreover, the research predominantly focuses on static image advertisements, which might not capture the complexity and dynamics of multimedia ads, such as videos or interactive formats. As for future directions, it would be pertinent to expand the dataset to encompass a broader array of advertisement types and cultural contexts, ensuring a more comprehensive and globally relevant model. Incorporating multimodal data sources, such as audio cues from video ads, could enhance the richness of the analysis. Additionally, exploring real-time feedback mechanisms where viewers' reactions and engagement levels are monitored could offer a more holistic understanding of the effectiveness of persuasion strategies, bridging the gap between prediction and actual consumer response.

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